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Research Article

**ASSOCIATION OF LIFE AND WORKING STATUS: A SURVEY
HELD ON THE WORKING WOMEN OF GANGA RAM
HOSPITAL, LAHORE**¹Dr. Muhammad Kashif ul Ehsan, ²Dr. Momina Shahzad Bajwa, ²Dr. Noor E Jawairia¹Senior Registrar Abwa Medical College and Research Hospital Khurianwala Faisalabad²Department of Community Medicine Gujranwala Medical College Gujranwala**Abstract:**

Objective: The research purpose is to find what impact working status has upon the life of a working woman who works at a teaching hospital.

Methodology: The research method adopted for the survey at a university hospital (Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore) is questionnaire. The survey was conducted from September, 2016 - July, 2017. To satisfy study objectives, the Questionnaire was designed to receive and record a better demographic profile of each patient. Informed consent with ensured confidentiality were provided in written form to fulfil requirements of research ethics. Data analysis was carried out through SPSS software.

Results: A total of 200 female subjects with 29.04 year of mean age were chosen and interviewed. Among them, 53.51% were married and 67.01% had more than grade-twelve education. Women working because of 'need' 31.50% (63), and because of home responsibility 41.50% (83), with women who received support from family 57.50% (115) and extra understanding 77.50% (155). A percentage of 61.50 (123) women promoted working women, having better status than non-working and the same number felt not having ample time to spend with family. According to 52.50% (105) respondents, disadvantages could be neglected considering financial benefits. Among married respondents, 40.0% (80) stated that working status is better for married women and her children and 40.05% (81) considered non-working women and their children to be better. According to 71.0% (142), working women has increased confidence than non-working. A percentage of 40.05 (81) women thought that financial support from women effects the self-esteem of husbands negatively.

Conclusions: It is a fact that working women face many difficulties in carrying out responsibilities of home and children thus requiring more studies to find ways of providing better working conditions which also support their home situations in our society.

Key Words: Women health, Women status (WS), Working women (WW), Women's role.

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INTRODUCTION:

With the increase in overall living costs and industrialization, women are bound to work to support their family and earn some extra living. For example, Sri Lanka's 6.60 million labour and more than 50% population are women [1]. Unfortunately, status of working women is considered 2nd class comparing working men [2,3]. Also, it is against tradition. This drastic change leaves deep concerns about working women facing difficulties in fulfilling home needs [4,5]. Due to work stress, increase depression and anxiety leaves working women incapable of looking after their family [6]. Reports also states that non-working women have less tendency towards activities promoting health than working women [7]. Working women, despite of having less time to spend with families, do more than housewives do for their families [8]. Pakistan faces the same deep concerns regarding working women. In nineties, thirteen percent of the women made among the female labours. A report states that women living in rural areas of Pakistan work from twelve to fifteen hours a day, the same goes for women living in urban [9]. With this loads of work, receiving little regard develops psychological and physical health issues among working women. It is very important to remove the guilt of these women of not being able to fulfil home and family needs comparing to housewives [10]. The aforementioned background necessitates the need to research impacts of working status on the life of a working woman.

METHODOLOGY:

The research method adopted for the survey at a university hospital (Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore) is questionnaire. The survey was conducted from September, 2016 - July, 2017. Family physicians (12 in number) receive 150 family patients on daily basis at centre. An in-depth literature review with patients' and colleagues input helped in developing

Questionnaire by major investigator. The data in questionnaire included education, marital status, and age to be included in the demographic profile of patients. Questions were oriented towards the research purpose. Being the national language of Pakistan, questions were in both "Urdu" and "English" language. Before the final administration of Questionnaire, a pilot interview was carried out with co-investigators. All the co-investigators agreed upon one way of administrating questionnaire to achieve uniformity. The patients waiting outside the office of physician for consultation were taken as subjects for questionnaire. Patients who were willing to participate were interviewed. No exact time schedule was followed throughout study. Being a descriptive research, no specific sample size was selected. Informed consent with ensured confidentiality was achieved to fulfil research ethics. Patients interviewed were based on convenience and availability, not with 'systematic' random selection of subjects. Data was managed through computer software "SPSS".

RESULTS:

A total of 200 female subjects with 29.04 year of mean age were chosen and interviewed. Among them, 53.51% were married, 67.01% had more than 12th grade education and 40.50% belonged to Teaching profession [Table – I]. Women working because of needs were 31.50% (63) and 41.50% (83) found fulfilling responsibilities of home difficult due to it. Family support and extra understanding was received by 57.50% (115) and 77.50% (155) respectively. Women who felt inadequate time for themselves were 61.50% (123). Women with domestic help were 44.50% (89) and 21.50% (43) felt unsafe at work. Being unable to spend more time with family due to work, 46.01% (92) women felt guilty [Table – II].

Table – I: Demographic Profile of the respondents

Parameter		Number	Percentage
Mean Age in years		29.05	
(Standard deviation)		-6.7	
Gender	Males	0	0
	Females	200	100
Marital Status	Married	107	53.5
	Single	91	45.5
	Others	2	1
Educational Status	Illiterate	17	8.5
	Can read & write	5	2.5
	Grade V education	10	5
	Grade VIII education	14	7
	Grade X education	20	10
	Grade XII education/	30	15
	Diploma Graduate	77	38.5
	Post-graduate	27	13.5
Occupation	Accountant/saleswomen	18	9
	Doctor	6	3
	Secretary/Librarian	4	2
	Teacher	81	40.5
	Maid/Domestic servant	23	11.5
	Engineer/lawyer	11	5.5
	Beautician /Dietitian	14	7
	Social worker	18	9
	Tailor	8	4
	Police women	1	0.5
	Laborer	8	4
	Nurse	3	1.5
	Others	5	2.5

Table – II: Respondent's views on Working Women issues

Question/Response		Number	Percentage
Reason to work	Own choice	84	42
	Need	63	31.5
	Both	53	26.5
Difficult to carryout home responsibilities because of Job?	Yes	83	41.5
	No	98	49
	Don't know	19	9.5
Do you receive understanding from your family because you work?	Yes	155	77.5
	No	45	22.5
Do you receive extra support from your family because you work?	Yes	115	57.5
	No	85	42.5
Do you find it difficult to look after your family members because you work?	Yes	80	40
	No	120	60
Do you feel who don't have time for yourself because you work?	Yes	123	61.5
	No	77	38.5
Is domestic help available to you?	Yes	89	44.5
	No	111	55.5
Do you feel harassed at work?	Yes	43	21.5
	No	157	78.5
Do you feel guilty that you don't give time to your family because of job?	Yes	92	46
	No	108	54
Confidence among children of working women is higher than non- working women?	Yes	106	53
	No	36	18
	Don't know	58	29
Children of working women perform better than those of non- working women in practical life?	Yes	104	52
	No	29	14.5
	Don't know	67	33.5
Do you feel better off working than not working?	Yes	129	64.5
	No	37	18.5
	Don't know	34	17

Table – III: Respondent’s views on Working Women issues

Questions	Responses	Number	Percentage
The status of working women is better than non-working women in our society?	Yes	123	61.5
	No	51	25.5
	Don't Know	26	13
Financial benefits outweigh other disadvantages for the working women?	Yes	105	52.5
	No	57	28.5
	Don't Know	38	19
Would you give up working if you had a choice?	Yes	60	30
	No	109	54.5
	Don't Know	31	15.5
Do you agree that in future all women will have to work?	Yes	126	63
	No	31	15.5
	Don't Know	43	21.5
Marriage prospects are better for working woman than non-working woman?	Yes	81	40.5
	No	60	30
	Don't Know	59	29.5
Marriage prospects for working women’s children are better than non- working women?	Yes	80	40
	No	45	22.5
	Don't Know	75	37.5
Confidence in working women is higher than non-working women?	Yes	142	71
	No	27	13.5
	Don't Know	31	15.5

Working woman's ability to be financially independent has negative impact on husband's self-esteem?	Yes	81	40.5
	No	66	33
	Don't Know	53	26.5
In-laws of a working woman do not support her to work?	Yes	67	33.5
	No	73	36.5
	Don't Know	60	30
Would you want your daughter to work if you had one?	Yes	105	52.5
	No	43	21.5
	Don't Know	52	26
Do you believe environment is less conducive for working women than working men?	Yes	108	54
	No	92	46

According to 53.01% (106), children of working women has more confidence comparing non-working women. According to 52.01% (104) felt children of working women performed better in practical life comparing to children of non-working women. Also, 64.50% (129) women felt better while working than being non-worker [Table – II].

According to 61.50% (123) women, working women status is better than those of not working. Hundred and five (52.50%) felt financial uplift outweighs some other disadvantages. Respondents willing to give up work if they had choice were 30.01% (60).

Respondents agreed on the point that all future women will work were 63.02% (126). Prospects of working women children and marriage is better than of not working and their children according to 40.01% (80) and 40.50% (81) respectively. According to 71.0% (142), working women has increased confidence than non-working. A percentage of 40.05 (81) women thought that financial support from women effects the self-esteem of husbands negatively. [Table – III].

DISCUSSION:

To fulfil research purpose, and valid conclusions, a large number of subjects with good educational background and from labour to professionals were interviewed. However, results are not general for all population as we selected subjects who came to teaching hospital for treatment. As respondents visiting a modern hospital were mostly educated, we can expect relatively more difficult situations for the working class of outside community. Yet our study forms a valuable base for coming extensive studies on improving working women lives.

Women working because of needs were 31.50% (63) and 41.50% (83) found fulfilling responsibilities of home difficult due to work. Such findings prove the value of concern about bad economic status due to which the number of working women is increasing yet having no solutions for attending family with plenty of time. It is therefore, required to find ways to resolve this issue.

Almost half of the working women had the privilege of receiving domestic help but we must consider situations of those women with no or little domestic help. A large number of women has been harassed at their work which arouses urgent resolution. A considerable number of women working have little time for themselves and almost half of them contain guilt because of not spending time with family due to work. This situation promotes actions for improvement of situations for working class of women in our society.

As a number of working women feel that their children do better in practical life and are more confident than of children of non-working women, it is required to do a deep study on this claimed difference. Feeling better while working and considering working women status to be better also testifies that working conditions are improving for working women. On the other hand, a percentage of 30 working women would quit if given choice testifies that is quite a room for improvement. This is also a fact that financial compensation does not fill the gap of spending time with family, hence the division among working women whether financial benefits outweigh the disadvantages or not. A surprising fact that most of the women will work in future, according to working women, testifies that economy is deteriorating which forces women to support their families by working. Some of the working women considers prospects of marriage to be increased for them and their children due to working status. Not only financial support but also social interactions increases prospects of working women. According to majority of working women,

confidence is higher in them comparing to non-working women. This is due to the challenges they face during work which also improves their personalities. Also, a large number of respondents consider working to have negative impressions on husbands' self-esteem. To find answers and remedies to that, a further in-depth study is required.

CONCLUSIONS:

It is a fact that working women face many hurdles in fulfilling their home responsibilities and it is required to do further studies to find out ways of improving their home situation as well as working conditions in society.

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